

THERMOPHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS:

A STATE-OF-THE-ART ASSESSMENT

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Abstract

Extensive research has been performed in the area of mechanical properties of composite materials, but much less has been conducted in the area of thermophysical properties. The Department of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering at the University of Delaware is presently involved in an effort to characterize some of the thermophysical properties of selected composite materials. The first step in this effort is an ongoing effort to collect and analyze as much of the existing literature as possible concerning the thermophysical properties of composite materials, concentrating on thermal conductivity and diffusivity, specific heat, and coefficient of thermal expansion. The material systems considered include long and short fiber systems as well as particulate systems, and properties are studied along the fiber axis as well as transverse to it.

This summary of the literature and comparative analysis attempts to determine how well the experimental literature has been developed concerning these properties, how the experimental results tabulated so far compare with the theoretical predictions, and what new needs are evident for future research. The results show that certain material systems and properties have been well-researched, while others have been virtually ignored. Opportunities for further research in this area could include characterization of metal-matrix and polymer composites other than graphite-epoxy, development of a data base for thermal diffusivity and specific heat of composite materials, development of methods of predicting specific heat and thermal diffusivity, and development of more accurate and repeatable experimental methods of determining thermophysical properties.

Introduction

More than half of the experimental literature on this topic concerns the coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) of composite materials, which is probably due to the importance of this property in problems of thermal stress. Most of the remaining experimental work is concerned with thermal conductivity, while very little work has been performed on heat capacity and thermal diffusivity. Most of the studies have focused on graphite/epoxy materials, while a few researchers have studied metal matrix composites, other organic composites, plastics, and ceramics. Table 1 shows the concentration of the experimental literature in the properties of thermal expansion and thermal conductivity and in the graphite/epoxy materials.

The theoretical literature shows the opposite concentration. Most of the theoretical research is concerned with thermal conductivity, while only a few papers, including the one by Schapery (1), are concerned with thermal expansion. The theoretical literature is very sparse on heat capacity and thermal diffusivity, with most researchers using a rule-of-mixtures approach to predict these properties.

Experimental Studies

Five papers, representative of the experimental literature, will be emphasized here. These are the works by Han and Boyee (2) on the thermal conductivity and thermal diffusivity of graphite/epoxy composites, Taylor, et al. (3) on Carbon/Carbon materials, Touloukian and Ho (4), Askins (5), and Christian and Campbell (6) on metal matrix composites.

Han and Boyee (2) experimentally determined thermal conductivity and thermal diffusivity values for a graphite/epoxy composite material, as shown in Table 2. The material was composed of unidirectional fibers embedded in the epoxy matrix. Experiments were performed to determine the effective thermal conductivity and thermal diffusivity of the material in the three orthogonal directions. Thermal conductivity and thermal diffusivity values were reported, but only one fiber volume fraction of material was used. This method was found to be simple and reliable, which satisfied another of the experimental objectives. Greater sensitivity would be obtained by testing materials of lower fiber volume fractions.

Several researchers have contributed general thermophysical property data on composite materials. Taylor (3) measured thermal conductivity, bulk density, thermal diffusivity, electrical resistivity, and coefficient of thermal expansion for fine-weave Carbon/Carbon composite materials. The Kohlrausch technique and a multiproperty apparatus were used to measure thermal conductivity, while the laser flash technique was used to measure thermal diffusivity. Thermal expansion was measured using a quartz dual rod dilatometer. The data are presented in both graphical and tabular form in the text. Thermal conductivity and thermal diffusivity values show a marked decrease with increasing temperature. Thermal expansion is slightly negative below 800 K, and slightly positive at higher temperatures. Accuracies within 3 percent were claimed for all of the measurements.

Several researchers have compiled or measured thermophysical property data on a number of different materials and have published them in compendium form. One of the most complete of these studies was done by Touloukian and Ho (4). They compiled thermophysical property data on seven selected aerospace materials from many reputable research papers. Three of the materials were composites. These were graphite/epoxy, boron/epoxy, and glass/epoxy. The data were compiled for thermal expansion coefficients, thermal conductivity,

Table I. Experimental Studies on Materials and Properties

Material Property	Gr/Ep	Gr/Polyimide	C/C	B/Ep	Gl/Ep	Other Organics	MMC	Ceramics	Plastics
Thermal Expansion	(4), (5), (16),(18), (19),(29)	(5),(17), (19)	(3), (26)	(4)	(4), (24)	(5), (16), (22),(31)	(6),(14), (16),(27), (30)	(21)	-
Thermal Conductivity	(2),(4), (5),(23)	(5),(17)	(3)	(4)	(4)	(5)	(14),(28)	-	(15),(25)
Specific Heat	(4), (5)	(5),(17)	-	(4)	(4)	(5)	(17)	-	-
Thermal Diffusivity	(2)	-	(3)	-	(4)	-	-	(21)	(25)

Table II. Summary of Effective Conductivities and Effective Diffusivities (2)

Test Run	Effective Conductivity k (BTU/hr-°F-ft)	Effective Diffusivity α (ft ² /sec)	Remarks
XQ	3.59	3.3×10^{-5}	Heat flow along fiber axis
XT	3.66	3.0×10^{-5}	
Average	3.63	3.15×10^{-5}	
YQ	0.452 0.459	2.0×10^{-6} 2.7×10^{-6}	Heat flow transverse to fibers and specimen slabs
YT	0.431 0.451	2.2×10^{-6} 2.8×10^{-6}	
Average	0.448	2.4×10^{-6}	
ZQ	0.700	3.19×10^{-6}	Heat flow transverse to fibers, paral- lel to slabs
ZT	0.590	2.71×10^{-6}	
Average	0.645	2.95×10^{-6}	
M	0.136	8.5×10^{-7}	Heat flow nor- mal to resin slabs, con- stant heat flux

thermal diffusivity, specific heat, and heat of fusion. All five of these properties were discussed, the method of data collection and reduction was explained, and the data were given in graphical and tabular form. All references used were credited. The papers used were critically evaluated first, which involved evaluating the reliability and validity of the data and related information, resolving disagreements in conflicting data, correlating data with respect to the controlling parameters, and comparing the results with analytical and theoretical predictions. In addition, experimental technique was reviewed for any possible unreported stray errors, stray heat flows, or heat losses. The experiment was also reviewed to see if errors were minimized and to see if the boundary conditions used in the experiment agreed with those of the theory.

Another extensive work in the area of experimental determinations of thermophysical properties is the paper of Askins (5). Askins developed engineering data on a number of composite materials of interest to the aerospace industry. The data include mechanical properties as well as thermal expansion, thermal conductivity, specific heat, and glass transition temperature.

The materials included four graphite/epoxies, SiC/epoxy, and graphite/polyimide composites. The specimens were prepared and fabricated by the author. Tests included specific heat, zero-degree and 90-degree thermal conductivity, and zero-degree, +/- 45-degree, and 90-degree thermal expansion for each material. The results showed that thermal conductivity and specific heat increased with increasing temperature for all six materials. The coefficient of thermal expansion seemed relatively independent of temperature except for the high-modulus graphite fiber system which showed a CTE decrease with increasing temperature, and the silicon-carbide system which showed an increasing CTE with increasing temperature.

Christian and Campbell (6) evaluated the mechanical and physical properties of several advanced metal-matrix composites. The materials included boron/aluminum, BORSIC/aluminum, BORSIC/titanium/aluminum, and BORSIC/stainless steel/aluminum. The physical tests were thermal expansion and specific heat measurements from 77 to 644 K. Nondestructive evaluation, volume percentage determinations, and metallographic examinations were performed before the testing began. The results showed that the low-conductivity BORSIC and boron fibers effectively controlled the matrix expansion in the fiber direction. The specific heat values fell between those of boron and aluminum throughout the temperature range.

An example of the data being obtained in the experimental literature is shown in Figure 1. This figure highlights the obvious temperature dependence of the thermal conductivity of graphite/epoxy composites. In addition, scatter in the data, which in this case approaches 50 percent of the magnitude of the measurement, is also shown. Scatter of this magnitude is characteristic of much of the experimental literature. In addition, when an error analysis is not made, it becomes difficult to assess the accuracy of the data.

Another example of the available data is shown in Figure 2. This figure shows that the addition of boron or BORSIC fibers to an aluminum matrix decreases the thermal expansion somewhat in the direction transverse to the fibers and drastically reduces the thermal expansion in the fiber direction. The thermal expansion is also shown to be very temperature dependent. Scatter is not shown in this figure due to the limited number of data points given.

Thermal expansion is very dependent on the material, the direction relative to the fibers, and temperature, as shown in Figure 3. Thermal expansion is extremely dependent on temperature in the direction transverse to the fibers except for Carbon/Carbon, but is less dependent on temperature in the fiber direction. The expansion versus temperature curve is especially flat for graphite/epoxy composites in the fiber direction. Boron/epoxy and glass/epoxy composites show a negative CTE relative to 300 K. Carbon/Carbon also shows a negative CTE in the transverse direction, which remains very flat even up to 1000 K.

A comparison of the thermal conductivities of various composites is shown in Figure 4. The high thermal conductivity of the metal matrix materials is expected, as is the temperature dependence of most of the materials. The exceptions are the Carbon/Carbon, which has a negative temperature dependence, and the boron/epoxy material, which has almost no temperature dependence in the fiber direction. Where two curves appear for the same material, the higher thermal conductivity is in the fiber direction. All other data are taken in the fiber direction except for Carbon/Carbon, which is taken in the transverse direction. There is a wide range of values given for the thermal conductivity of graphite/epoxy from a variety of sources, which may be indicative of the different graphite fibers used by the different researchers or may be more scatter in the data.

Figure 1 - Example of scatter typically found in experimental data (5).

Figure 2 - Thermal expansion of aluminum with Boron or BORSIC fiber additions (6).

Figure 3 - Dependence of thermal expansion on temperature, orientation, and material.

The scarcity of thermal diffusivity data is shown in Figure 5. The inverse temperature dependence of the Carbon/Carbon is consistent with the thermal conductivity data by the same researcher in Figure 4. However, the inverse temperature dependence of the glass/epoxy is inconsistent with the thermal conductivity data given by the same researcher in Figure 4. The three data points for graphite/epoxy represent, from top to bottom, thermal diffusivity in the fiber direction, the transverse direction, and the thermal diffusivity of the neat resin.

The temperature dependence of the heat capacity is shown in Figure 6. The heat capacity of the materials represented here increases approximately by a factor of three in a temperature difference of 500 K. All of the materials use the same matrix except for the graphite/polyimide, which is even more temperature dependent. The scarcity of data is evident here too, as this data came from only two papers, published in 1977 and 1982.

Theoretical Studies

Of the theoretical papers in the literature, six will be discussed in detail here. These include the papers by Springer and Tsai (7) on the thermal conductivity of unidirectional materials, Behrens (8) on the thermal conductivity of composite materials, Nomura and Chou (9) on bounds for the effective thermal conductivities of short-fiber composites, Han and Cosner (10) on the effective thermal conductivity of fibrous composites, Zimmerman (11) on predicting the transverse thermal conductivity of composite materials, and

Thermal Conductivity vs. Temperature

Figure 4 - Thermal conductivity of composite materials.

Schapery (1) on the thermal expansion of composite materials. In addition, Progelhof (12) presented an excellent review of all of the major theories for predicting the thermal conductivity of composite materials.

Springer and Tsai (7) published the first significant paper on the thermal conductivity of composite materials in 1967. They developed a method to predict the thermal conductivity of unidirectional materials using an analogy with the shear loading equations. Numerical techniques were used for the solution of this analogy. The problem considered was that of unidirectional fibers embedded in a matrix, and the filaments were assumed to be arranged in a rectangular periodic array. Thermal contact resistance between the fiber and matrix was neglected, and the matrix and fiber were each assumed to be locally homogeneous and isotropic. A simple series model was also demonstrated, and comparisons between the two methods were made. The two methods agree within about five percent for cylindrical fibers and fiber volume fractions below 60 percent, as shown in Figure 7. The theoretical models were compared with experimental data obtained from another researcher. For the cylindrical fiber, the shear loading analogy better predicts the thermal conductivity. The series model predicts the low-ratio material extremely well. Most theoretical models are difficult to compare with experimental results because most models only show thermal conductivity versus volume fraction, whereas most experimental data is in the form of thermal conductivity versus temperature for a given fiber volume fraction.

Figure 5 - Thermal diffusivity of composite materials.

Figure 6 - Heat capacity of composite materials.

Figure 7 - Comparison between experimental data and the results of the shear loading analogy and thermal models. Experimental data from Thornburg and Pears for glass-plastic ($k_f/k_m = 4.4$) and graphite fabric-plastic ($k_f/k_m = 666$) composites are shown (7).

Another approach to theoretical predictions of thermal conductivity of composite materials was presented by Behrens (8). This method is known in solid-state physics as the method of long waves. Thermal waves are considered which are long in comparison to the intercomponent spacing. Expressions are obtained for the average thermal conductivities by calculating the damping coefficients in the principal directions of the medium. This method has the advantage of being applicable to composites with an arbitrary number of constituents. Results of the calculations were given for three different two-phase composites with isotropic constituents. In addition, the variation of the thermal conductivities in the three principal directions with fiber volume fraction was given.

Nomura and Chou (9) presented the results of a study to determine the bounds of the effective thermal conductivities of short-fiber composite materials. The method consists of adopting a perturbation expansion of the local strain field using a Green's function tensor. The correlation of thermal conductivity is evaluated based on the characteristics of the geometry and distribution of the component phases. The bounds are then determined from a variational treatment. The upper and lower bounds thus presented are tighter than those of Hashin and Shtrikman (13), as shown in Figure 8. For continuous fibers, the bounds converge to a straight line. The two sets of bounds are in close agreement when the fiber volume fraction is less than 0.5. The large uncertainty in most of the experimental data makes either set of bounds a valid predictor of thermal conductivity when the fiber volume fraction is less than 0.5. In addition, in this range either the lower or upper bound could be used.

Han and Cosner (10) presented the results of a study to solve a two-region steady-state heat conduction equation analytically and numerically. The purpose of this study was to determine the steady-state effective thermal conductivities of fiber-matrix composite materials and to investigate a class of heat conduction problems where the proximity effects of the embedded fibers are significant. Two cases were studied, which were unidirectional fibers embedded in a matrix and a 0/90 configuration in which unidirectional tapes are overlaid perpendicular to each other. Prior knowledge of the geometry and thermal conductivities of the constituent materials is assumed. The intent of this paper was to present a continuum model with an effective thermal conductivity rather than a discrete microstructure model. They sought to establish bounds by which the modelling approach could be strengthened and enlarged. The effective thermal conductivity was found to be sensitive to fiber orientation, and the effective conductivity ratio was found to be principally governed by the distance between two adjacent fibers measured along the heat flow line.

Zimmerman (11) continued the work of Han and Cosner in a later study of analytical models for predicting the transverse thermal conductivity of unidirectional and bidirectional composite materials. These models were based on the Rayleigh solution and on a one-dimensional conduction analysis and are then compared with the numerical results obtained by Han and Cosner (10). For unidirectional and bidirectional composite materials not having voids or other major defects, these models predict transverse thermal conductivity with reasonable accuracy. With the adjustment factors presented, the two models predict the Han/Cosner numerical results to within several percent. For normal ranges of the variables involved, primarily fiber volume fraction, the models have been adjusted to give accuracies to within one percent. In Figure 9, the two models are compared to the Han/Cosner data and to the upper and lower bounds. This shows that the model based on the Rayleigh solution predicts the Han/Cosner data extremely well when the fiber volume fraction is in the normal usable range, below 0.75. The one-dimensional conduction analysis model is also a good predictor.

Figure 8 - The variation of k_{11}^*/k_m with filler volume fraction for a graphite/epoxy system, using $k_f = 60$ BTU/(hr-ft² - °F/in), $k_m = 1.7$ BTU/(hr-ft² - °F/in), and $l/d = 1$. Solid lines: Nomura and Chou (9), broken line: Hashin and Shtrikman (13).

Figure 10 shows the usual ranges of the tow thermal conductivity and the matrix thermal conductivity for several composite material systems. The metal matrix materials have a high matrix conductivity and thus a low ratio of tow-to-matrix thermal conductivity, as expected. The organic materials also behave as expected, with a high fiber conductivity and thus a high ratio.

Schapery (1) saw the need for a method to predict the effective coefficient of thermal expansion of a composite material in terms of the constituent properties. His purpose was to develop a new method for calculating the upper and lower bounds on the CTE of isotropic and anisotropic composites with isotropic phases. The complementary and potential energy principles of thermoelasticity theory were used in conjunction with a procedure for minimizing the difference between the upper and lower bounds. For certain important cases, the bounds were found to coincide. Explicit formulas were given for the volumetric and linear CTE of elastic and viscoelastic materials. Numerical examples were compared with results from the literature.

Conclusions

Several conclusions can be drawn from this study. The most obvious conclusion is that there are gaps in the thermophysical data on composite materials that should be filled. Several materials should be characterized, including metal matrix composites, organic composites other than graphite/epoxy, and new materials as they are invented. Heat capacity and thermal diffusivity data are needed on almost all materials. In addition, scatter in the data must be minimized, either through efforts to minimize heat losses in the experiments or through better reporting of heat losses and other sources of error.

Figure 9 - Comparison of Rayleigh equation, one-dimensional conduction equation, and Han and Cosner (10) numerical data (11).

Figure 10 - Ranges of tow and matrix thermal conductivity (11).

More theoretical work is needed in thermal diffusivity and specific heat of composite materials, to determine whether or not the rule-of-mixtures approach is valid and to determine methods of determining these properties when the properties of the material constituents are not known a priori. There is a need to predict these properties as well as it is now possible to predict thermal conductivity. There is also a need to be able to predict the temperature dependence of thermal conductivity.

Better reporting of experimental work is needed. It is very frustrating to attempt to compare the data of more than one experiment when insufficient information is given. Heat losses should first be minimized, then accounted for and reported. Other information such as test temperature, fiber volume fraction, void content, layup orientation and cure cycle, and any other relevant information should be given in the report. When this information is given, the data can be meaningfully evaluated.

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